

Trend in the Seroprevalence of Transfusion Transmissible Infections (TTIs) from 2019 to 2023 at the Blood Transfusion Service of the Buea Regional Hospital, Southwest Region, Cameroon

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Abstract:

Background: Transfusion-transmissible infections (TTIs) are of significant public health concern, as they can be transmitted through blood transfusions. Monitoring the trends and prevalence of TTIs is crucial for ensuring the safety of the blood supply and implementing effective preventive measures. This study aimed to analyze the trend in seroprevalence of TTIs, including HIV, hepatitis B (HBV), hepatitis C (HCV), and syphilis (TPHA), among blood donors in the Buea Regional Hospital (BRH) from 2019 to 2023. **Materials and Methods:** This retrospective study was conducted using data from the Buea Regional Hospital Blood Transfusion Service. The study population included all blood donors who donated blood from January 2019 to December 2023. Serological testing for TTIs was performed using standard diagnostic methods. The prevalence of

each TTI was calculated for each year, and the trends were analyzed using statistical tests and expressed as frequency tables, Chi square, logistic regression. Significance was set at $p=0.05$. **Results:** A total of 11,256 donors were tested and 919 (8.12%) blood donors tested positive for at least one TTI agent during the study period. The overall positivity rates were 8.23%, 9.48%, 6.65%, 8.29%, and 8.24% for 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. The prevalence of individual TTIs showed significant variations, with TPHA being the most prevalent (2.96%), followed by HBV (2.58%), HCV (1.15%), and HIV (1.24%). Socio-demographic factors, such as gender, marital status, occupation, and age, were found to be significantly associated ($p<0.001$) with the odds of testing positive for a TTI. **Conclusion:** The trend

in the prevalence of TTIs among blood donors in the Buea Health Area was characterized by fluctuations over the five-year period.

Keywords: *blood transfusion, blood donation, infections, socio-demographic factors.*

Introduction

Blood donation remains vital in saving lives and improving the health of millions of people worldwide. However, this therapy is associated with various adverse effects including the transmission of infectious diseases. In 2010, Choudhury reported a 1-2 per 1000 risk for blood recipients of contaminated blood to get viral, bacterial or parasitic infections (Choudhury, 2010). Approximately, 4 million people globally have been infected with HIV by transfusing unsafe blood (WHO, 2017). Therefore, recipients of transfused blood stand a high risk of potential infection from transfusion transmissible infections (TTIs). The main infections associated to blood transfusions are the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), and syphilis and the spread of these infections progresses more in less developed countries (Yang *et al.*, 2016; Kebede *et al.*, 2017). Tagny *et al.* reported that approximately 25% of blood units donated in Francophone Africa are contaminated with blood borne pathogens (Tagny *et al.*, 2012). Some studies on TTIs markers in some towns in Cameroon revealed a seroprevalence of 4.1% (HIV), 20.4% (HBV) 4.8% (HCV) and 8.1% for syphilis (Noubiap *et al.*, 2013; Ducancelle *et al.*, 2013; Moukoko *et al.*, 2014). A steady decline in the prevalence of HCV and syphilis serological markers have been reported among blood donors in Yaoundé, Cameroon within a five-year period (Tagny *et al.*, 2016). In an effort to improve the quality and safety of blood delivered at blood banks in Cameroon, various initiatives have been put in place by different structures. These bodies include the Ministry of Public Health (MoPH), the US Centers for Disease Control (CDC), the Safe Blood for Africa Foundation™ (SBFA), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the US CDC/PEPFAR (US President's Emergency

Plan for AIDS Relief). Strategies employed by these bodies include education, sensitization, immunization and trainings. Awareness is being created through regular campaigns, continuous education and free screening for TTIs. With regards to improving blood safety at the blood transfusion centers, these structures provide technical support which encompasses situational assessment, blood collection, blood testing, quality assurance and training of personnel. These actions are geared at establishing sustainable blood services according to the guidelines and recommendations of WHO for developing countries (PEPFAR, 2013; SBFA, 2016; CDC, 2018). In line with WHO recommendations, a National Blood Transfusion Program (NBTP) and a national policy on blood transfusion were established in Cameroon in 2003 to oversee activities related to safe blood donation (WHO, 2017). Although different studies related to blood donations and prevalence of TTIs have been reported in Cameroon (Mbanya *et al.*, 2008; Noubiap *et al.*, 2013; Moukoko *et al.*, 2014; Tagny *et al.*, 2016; Tagny *et al.*, 2017), none so far, has been reported for the Buea Regional Hospital Blood Transfusion Service (BRHBTS). Furthermore, no regular monitoring of TTIs markers has been conducted at this hospital which is a major transfusion centre and one of SBFA initiative reference centers. This study had as objective to provide novel data on the seropositivity rates and trend of serological markers of the four conventional TTIs in blood donations from 2019 to 2023 at the BRHBTS.

Materials and Methods

Study Site

This study was carried out at the blood transfusion service of the Buea Regional Hospital which receives patients not only from

within the Buea municipality, but also from its environs and beyond. Buea is the administrative headquarter of the South-west region of Cameroon. The Buea Regional Hospital is one of the largest government hospitals in the region and serves as a referral hospital for approximately two million people in the regional. The hospital is located in the Buea road health area of the Buea Health District, along the Long Street Road. This hospital was among the five pilot centers that were chosen by safe blood for Africa (SBFA) to serve as a reference blood transfusion center in Cameroon. It is a suitable site as it plays host to an HIV treatment center, the only haemodialysis and hepatitis treatment centers in the Southwest Region; and the largest blood transfusion service with the only blood depot in the Region.

Study Population

The study included all potential blood donors who presented themselves at the blood transfusion service for the purpose of blood donation from January, 2019 to December, 2023 at the Buea Regional Hospital.

Study Design

This was a retrospective cross-sectional study of all blood donations received at the Buea regional hospital. Hospital records were used to collect data on TTI positivity rate from 2019 to 2023 and described it in terms of person and time.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Those included in the study were individuals within the ages of 18 to 60 years, who presented as potential blood donors at the Buea Regional Hospital during the study period and who had completed the donor screening process.

Exclusion Criteria

Excluded from the study were individuals who did not provide consent for their data to be used in the study, and those with incomplete or missing records.

Sampling Technique

A total census sampling approach was used, where data from all eligible potential blood donors during the study period were included.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size consisted of all eligible potential blood donors who visited the Buea Regional Hospital from 2019 to 2023.

Laboratory Analysis

Donor evaluation

In line with guidelines, all potential donors go through an initial screening using a blood selection questionnaire. This was followed by the haemoglobin concentration measurement of those retained before proceeding to tests for TTIs.

Specimen Collection

Five microliters of venous blood samples collected from the potential blood donors were tested for the presence of HIV, HCV, HBV, and Syphilis antibodies or antigens using the appropriate laboratory testing kits. Standard operating procedures was followed for sample collection, processing, and testing to ensure accurate and reliable results. The blood specimens were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and serum samples were obtained for the detection of viral and bacterial infections.

Detection of viral and bacterial infections (HIV, HBV, HCV & TPPIs)

The national blood transfusion algorithm was applied for the screening and qualification of each blood sample. It states that the blood bags should be qualified using highly sensitive, specific, less costly and easy to manipulate tests to investigate for HIV, HBV, HCV, and TPHA obligatorily. The screening must be run in parallel (National Blood Transfusion Algorithm, 2017 Ed.). They must also be able to identify the antibodies or antigens sought after in order to reduce serological window when they are available.

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) Test

Following the national algorithm for HIV testing of blood donations in Cameroon, all blood bags were screened for HIV infection using two rapid diagnostic tests one being very sensitive Determine® HIV-1/2 Ag/Ab combo (Alere Medical Co.,™ Limited Matsuhidai, Matsudo-Shi, China) for the first-line test. The OraQuick (OraSure Technologies, Inc, Bethlehem) or HIV Ag/Ab (ReLab SAS, Parc Eurasante, France; 2020) served for second line test, allowing for distinction between HIV 1 and 2. Sensitivity and specificity were 100% and 98.93% respectively. Samples that were negative for the rapid diagnostic test screening, were further tested using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Fortress diagnostics™ HIV Ag/Ab 4th generation) which detect the viral antigens HIV-1 M (A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H), group O, group N and HIV-2 in the serum. It ran on the principle of two steps incubation “sandwich” which uses polystyrene microwell strips precoated with recombinant HIV antigens (recombinant HIV-1 gp41, gp120 and recombinant HIV-2 gp36) and anti-HIV p24 antigens. Testing was done following manufacturer’s procedure to measure the absorbance. Sample absorbance was compared to the cut-off value which was considered positive if greater than the cut-off and negative when less than or equal to the cut-off value. All positive bags were removed from the system and discarded.

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) Test

The screening for Hepatitis B surface antigens (HBsAg) was by One Step HBsAg Rapid Test (ACON Laboratories, Inc. 2017) with reported sensitivity and specificity of 95.16% and 99.95% respectively. This test is a qualitative lateral flow immunoassay for the detection of HBsAg in serum or plasma. The membrane of the test strip is pre-coated with anti-HBsAg antibodies capture on the test line region and rabbit anti-goat IgG on the control line region (ACON, 2017). All samples that were negative for the rapid test were further tested using ELISA test for surface antigens (Fortress diagnostics™ HBsAg, 2016). Sample absorbance was compared to the cut-off value which was

considered positive if greater than the cut-off and negative when less than or equal to the cut-off value. All positive bags were removed from the system and discarded.

HCV Test

The detection of Hepatitis C virus antibodies in the serum was done using both immunochromatographic RDT-based assay (One Step HCV Rapid Test by (ACON Laboratories, Inc. 2017). Immuno-enzymatic ELISA test (Fortress diagnostics™ Anti-HCV4th generation) was used to further screened those bags that were negative by RDT. Sample absorbance was compared to the cut-off value which was considered positive if greater than the cut-off and negative when less than or equal to the cut-off value. All positive bags were removed from the system and discarded.

Treponema pallidum (Syphilis) Test

For the detection of syphilis antibodies, a Treponemal antigen for specific anti-treponemal antibody (One Step TPHA Rapid Test) was used together with non-treponemal antigen for non-specific reagin antibody (RPR) (ACON, 2016).

Data Entry

A worksheet was created using Microsoft excel to enter some demographic parameters and transfusion transmitted infections (HIV, HBV, HCV, Syphilis) results. Consistency and validation checks were done to help in minimizing entry errors during data entry.

Data Analysis

The data was exported into R version 4.2.3 analysed using the same. Descriptive Statistics was used to summarize and describe socio-demographic characteristics and annual prevalence of positive cases for Transfusion-Transmissible Infections (TTIs) from 2019 to 2023 **using** frequencies and percentages. The trends and variations in the prevalence of the different TTIs (HIV, HBV, HCV, TPHA, VDRL) over the study period were analyzed using Chi-square tests. The rate of change in prevalence was calculated for each disease by comparing annual percentages. Positive, negative, or zero rates of change were

interpreted to understand the trends. Gamma regression models were employed to calculate both crude and adjusted odds ratios (ORs) for predictors including gender, marital status, occupation, age, and donor type. Confidence intervals (CIs) and p-values (0.05) were used to assess the significance and strength of these associations.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval for the study was gotten from the regional delegation of public health review board (No) and from the Institutional review board of the faculty of health sciences, university of Buea (No2024/2538-05/UB/SG/IRB/FHS).

Result

Descriptive Statistics

Out of a total of 11252 donors that were tested from between 2019 and 2023, there were more

male participants, 10859 (96.47%) than females 393 (3.39%). Religious affiliation was overwhelmingly Christians 11249 (99.94%), with a very small representation of other religion. There was a great diversity in the occupation of participant with most of the donors coming from the education and academia sectors 5187(46.08%), skilled trades 1462 (12.99%), agriculture and environment 514(4.57%). Additionally, the donors were categorised into donation type and age groups. The chief majority of participants were family replacement donors 6780 (60.49%), followed by paid donors 4245 (37.87%) and benevolent donors making the least with 184 (1.64%). The age range of donors was diverse with the majority 5959 (52.94) falling into the age bracket of 18-30 years. This was followed by the age group 31-30 (32.08%) and those above 40 years formed the minority. There was also a variation in the number of donors attended to which increased from one year to the next with the least registered in 2019 (1542) and the highest in 2023 (3555) (Table 1).

Table 1. Sociodemographic Distribution of Participants in the Study from January, 2019 to December, 2023

Variable	Category	n (%)
Gender	Male	10859 (96.47)
	Female	397 (3.53)
Age (Years)	18-30	5959 (52.94)
	31-40	3611 (32.08)
	41-50	1523 (13.53)
	51-60	152 (1.35)
	>60	11 (0.1)
Donor Type	Benevolent	184 (1.64)
	Family replacement	6780 (60.49)
	Remunerated	4245 (37.87)
Marital Status	Married	2830 (25.14)
	Single	8426 (74.86)
Occupation	Administrative & Clerical	36 (0.32)
	Agriculture & Environment	514 (4.57)
	Arts & Entertainment	83 (0.74)
	Business & Management	778 (6.91)
	Construction & Maintenance	3 (0.03)
	Education & Academia	5187 (46.08)
	Food & Hospitality	75 (0.67)
	Healthcare	151 (1.34)
	Sales & Retail	1 (0.01)

	Security & Protection	60 (0.53)
	Skilled Trades	1462 (12.99)
	Other	1650 (14.66)
Religion	Christian	11249 (99.94)
	Muslim	7 (0.06)
Total number tested/Years	2019	1542 (13.70)
	2020	1623 (14.42)
	2021	1908 (16.95)
	2022	2628 (23.35)
	2023	3555 (31.58)

Serprevalence of Transfusion Transmissible Infections (TTIs) from 2019 to 2023

Over the 5-year period from 2019 to 2023, a total of 919 (8.12%) blood donors in the BRHBTS tested positive for at least one transfusion-transmissible infection (TTI). The prevalence of these infections showed significant variations during this time. The overall positivity rates were

8.23%, 9.48%, 6.65%, 8.29%, and 8.24% in 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 respectively. While the prevalence increased significantly from 2019 to 2020 ($p=0.014$), it then suddenly decreased again significantly in 2021 ($p=0.021$). In 2022, the positivity rate increased again to 8.29% ($p<0.001$), before remaining relatively stable at 8.24% in 2023 ($p=0.712$) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Trend in Positivity of the Overall TTI Prevalence from 2019 to 2023

Positivity Rate of Individual Transfusion Transmissible Infections (TTIs)

Analysis of the individual TTIs revealed some interesting trends (Table 2). HIV prevalence decreased from 0.65% in 2019 to 0.16% in 2021, before sharply increasing to 2.13% in 2022 and falls significantly to 1.77% in 2023 ($p<0.001$), suggesting a resurgence in new cases. HBV prevalence remained relatively stable, fluctuating

between 2.25% and 3.05% over the 5-year period. In contrast, HCV prevalence showed significant fluctuations, peaking at 2.40% in 2020 before decreasing to 0.49% in 2022 and then increasing again to 1.07% in 2023 ($p<0.001$). This pattern may be indicative of changes in diagnostic practices or reporting accuracy. Syphilis (TPHA) prevalence displayed a steady upward trend, reaching its highest point of 2.96% in 2023 (Figure 2).

Table 2. Overall Prevalence of Each TTI per Year for the Study Period of 2019-2023

Year	HIV (n, %)	HBV (n, %)	HCV (n, %)	TPHA (n, %)	VDRL (n, %)
2019	10 (0.65)	47 (3.05)	21 (1.36)	42 (2.72)	7 (0.45)
2020	8 (0.49)	48 (2.96)	39 (2.40)	52 (3.20)	7 (0.43)
2021	3 (0.16)	43 (2.25)	18 (0.94)	62 (3.25)	1 (0.05)
2022	56 (2.13)	59 (2.25)	13 (0.49)	82 (3.12)	8 (0.30)
2023	63 (1.77)	93 (2.62)	38 (1.07)	95 (2.67)	4 (0.11)
Overall	140 (1.24)	290 (2.58)	129 (1.15)	333 (2.96)	27 (0.24)
X2	55.15	4.26	33.98	2.45	11.11
p-Value	<0.001	0.370	<0.001	0.653	0.025

Figure 2. Prevalence of the Different TTIs per Year from January, 2019 to December, 2023

Trends and Associated Socio-Demographic Factors of Blood Donors Regarding TTIs (2019-2023)

Socio-demographic analysis revealed that the odds of testing positive for a TTI was significantly higher among males (AOR: 2.11, $p=0.0029$), single individuals (AOR: 1.76,

$p<0.001$), and those in the education and academia sector (AOR: 10.07, $p=0.0029$). Age groups 31-40 (AOR: 1.99, $p<0.001$) and 41-50 (AOR: 2.43, $p<0.001$) also exhibited increased prevalence. Notably, paid donors had an extremely high odds ratio of 603.08, highlighting the substantial influence of donor type on TTI prevalence (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of Trends and Associated Socio-Demographic Factors of Blood Donors Regarding TTIs (2019-2023)

Predictor	COR	CI (95%)	P-value (COR)	AOR	CI (95%)	P-value
Male	6.14	(5.06-7.48)	<0.001	2.11	(1.40-3.17)	0.0029
Single	9.47	(8.01-11.23)	<0.001	1.76	(1.32-2.36)	<0.001
31-40	0.76	(0.66-0.87)	0.003	1.99	(1.57-2.53)	<0.001
41-50	0.71	(0.58-0.87)	0.007	2.43	(1.86-3.16)	<0.001
51-60	1.39	(0.71-2.74)	0.384	4.27	(2.37-7.69)	0.001
>60	1.32	(0.21-8.51)	0.837	2.08	(0.56-7.68)	0.651
Agriculture & Environment	1.73	(0.69-4.69)	0.446	1.41	(0.82-2.43)	0.664
Arts & Entertainment	2.34	(0.68-8.64)	0.313	1.92	(0.57-6.51)	0.485
Business & Management	1.52	(0.59-3.73)	0.555	1.77	(0.54-5.84)	0.468
Construction & Maintenance	2.47	(0.13-45.62)	0.732	1.11	(0.05-24.29)	0.972
Education & Academia	61.34	(17.84-211.76)	<0.001	10.07	(2.56-39.46)	0.003
Food & Hospitality	1.25	(0.39-3.36)	0.794	0.64	(0.24-1.74)	0.637
Healthcare	1.62	(0.56-4.48)	0.535	2.64	(1.22-5.72)	0.259
Other	1.51	(0.56-3.45)	0.554	1.46	(0.58-3.73)	0.625
Sales & Retail	0.11	(0.01-0.14)	0.545	0.12	(0.01-1.87)	0.601
Security & Protection	0.88	(0.43-1.16)	0.887	1.07	(0.22-5.15)	0.946
Skilled Trades	1.49	(0.55-4.46)	0.569	1.30	(0.29-5.66)	0.737
Social Services & Humanitarian Work	1.03	(0.12-13.83)	0.984	1.40	(0.21-9.24)	0.852
Technology & Engineering	1.58	(0.61-4.15)	0.525	1.38	(0.32-5.96)	0.688
Transportation & Logistics	2.01	(0.57-5.62)	0.324	1.41	(0.38-5.28)	0.663
Muslim	0.09	(0.01-1.40)	0.089	0.56	(0.09-3.39)	0.732
Family replacement donors	2.08	(1.08-4.01)	0.026	2.70	(1.38-5.29)	0.003
Paid donors	1100.40	(585.76-2057.58)	< 0.001	603.08	(288.24-1260.15)	<0.001

Discussion

We observed an overall increase in the seropositivity rate of all the four TTI markers with the rising being significant for HIV and HCV. The highest positivity rate for all the combined markers was in 200, followed by a steep fall in 2021 and then a steady rise between 2022 and 2023. The data in the current study shows some notable year-to-year variations in TTI prevalence. There was a significant decrease from 2020 (9.48%) to 2021 (6.65%), followed by a significant increase from 2021 to 2022 (8.29%). These fluctuations could be attributed to changes in donor screening protocols, improved testing methods, or shifts in the underlying epidemiology of TTIs in the population. Similar year-to-year variations have been reported in other settings such as the study by Omoregie *et*

al. in Nigeria found TTI prevalence ranging from 5.8% to 9.2% over a 5-year period (Omoregie *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, variations in TTI prevalence have also been linked to factors like seasonal patterns, regional differences, and changes in donor demographics (Rujeni *et al.*, 2021).

Over the observed five years, this study showed that 919 donors tested positive for at least one of the four TTI markers that were screened. These findings were similar to those observed in the studies conducted in eastern Ethiopia by Teklemeriam *et al.* (Teklemariam *et al.*, 2018) and by Birhaneselassi *et al.* (Birhaneselassie, 2016). The overall positivity rate for the TTI agent was found to be 8.12%, which is within the range reported by similar studies in different geographical regions such as a study conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa reported an overall TTI

seroprevalence between 5-15% among blood donors (Jayaraman *et al.*, 2010). Other studies in India and Bamenda found the overall TTI seroprevalence to be 9.5% (Gagandeep *et al.*, 2010) and 10.5% (Samje *et al.*, 2021) respectively, slightly higher than ours. A systematic review and meta-analysis pooled prevalence of TTIs in sub-Saharan Africa by Rujeni and colleagues reported an overall prevalence of 8.6% (Rujeni *et al.* 2021). More to this, Mbanya *et al.* reported a TTI prevalence of 7.8% in Cameroon (Mbanya *et al.* 2020) which is comparable to the 8.12% prevalence reported in the current study.

A noticeable trend of decline in the positivity rate was observed for HIV from 2011 to 2021 with a sudden sharp rise in positivity in 2022. This suggests a potential resurgence in HIV transmission among the studied blood donor population. Our observation in this study shows similar patterns of fluctuations in HIV prevalence as reported in a study in sub-Saharan Africa where HIV prevalence among blood donors was found to vary considerably over time, influenced by factors such as changes in donor demographics, testing strategies, and the success of HIV prevention programs (Jayaraman *et al.*, 2010). Another study in the United States also reported significant year-to-year variations in HIV prevalence among blood donors, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and targeted interventions (Zou *et al.*, 2004; Mobarki *et al.*, 2022).

In contrast, the HBV positivity remained relatively stable with minor fluctuations, culminating in a peak in 2023. This finding is consistent with other studies that have found HBV seroprevalence to be more consistent over time among blood donor populations (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Petruzzello *et al.*, 2016) but lower when compared to studies conducted in other cities of Cameroon (Ducancelle *et al.*, 2013; Tagny *et al.*, 2016b; Samje *et al.*, 2021). One of the reasons for the above observation could be the effectiveness of the initiation of children immunization program against HBV in 2000, and screening measures in this setting. The positivity rate of HCV was the lowest among all the four markers of TTIs in this study, with significant fluctuations in the trend over the

years. Remarkably, this was also the lowest observed when compared to other studies in Cameroon (Noubiap *et al.*, 2013; Moukoko *et al.*, 2014; Tagny *et al.*, 2017), Kenya (Onyango *et al.*, 2018) and Burkina Faso (Nagalo *et al.*, 2012) although higher than the observation in other countries such as 0.6% in Ethiopia (Shiferaw *et al.*, 2019), 0.20% in Southwest Ethiopia (Kebede *et al.*, 2017), and lower than the observation of 1.3% in Guyana (Leitch *et al.*, 2022), 1.7% in Bamenda (Samje *et al.*, 2021) and 1.21% in Mamfe (Ngomtcho *et al.*, 2024).

Our observation on the trend of syphilis is quite higher when compared with a study from Ethiopia (0.14%) (Kebede *et al.*, 2017) and lower than those of Rivers State in Nigeria (0.21%) (Okoh *et al.*, 2014). The TPHA (syphilis) prevalence displayed a steady upward trend, reaching its highest point in 2023. This aligns with studies that have reported an increasing trend in syphilis prevalence among blood donors in certain regions (Durro *et al.*, 2010; LE, 2021). The rising TPHA prevalence may be indicative of a need for enhanced screening, partner notification, and public health interventions to address syphilis transmission.

Comparing positivity rate to socio-demographic factors, the findings revealed that males had significantly higher odds (AOR: 2.11) of testing positive for TTIs is consistent with a systematic review and meta-analysis by Allain *et al.* reported that male gender was a significant risk factor for TTIs in sub-Saharan Africa (Allain *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, a study by Tessema *et al.* in Ethiopia found that being male was associated with a higher risk of TTIs (Tessema *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, the higher prevalence among single individuals (AOR: 1.76) is also supported by other research, such as a study by Mafirakureva *et al.* (2016) in Zimbabwe. Furthermore, the notably higher odds of TTIs among those in the education and academia sector (AOR: 10.07) is of key importance. While there is limited research specifically on this occupational group, a study by Mbanya *et al.* (2010) found that civil servants had a higher risk of TTIs compared to other occupations. The lack of significant associations for other occupations, such as healthcare workers, is somewhat surprising, as

this group is often considered at higher risk for TTIs. The increased prevalence of TTIs in the 31-40 and 41-50 age groups is consistent with findings from other studies, such as the systematic review by Allain *et al.* (2016). The extremely high odds ratio for paid donors (AOR: 603.08) underscores the well-established risk of TTIs among this donor population, as reported in numerous studies (e.g., Allain *et al.*, 2010; Nantulya *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

The data reveal a complex picture of TTI trends in the Buea Regional Hospital, with significant fluctuations and variations across different infections and socio-demographic factors. These findings underscore the importance of continuous monitoring and targeted interventions to address the evolving dynamics of transfusion-transmissible infections in the region.

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Competing Interests

None to declare.

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